

Coastal Waste and Its Impacts: A Review of Sources, Categories, and Consequences

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Abstract

Waste, particularly in coastal areas, has become a pressing environmental issue due to its increasing volume and harmful impacts. Defined by Indonesian law and various scholars, waste includes organic, inorganic, and hazardous materials, with diverse origins ranging from household to industrial activities. Coastal zones face significant threats as land-based and sea-based waste sources converge, exacerbated by human behavior, lack of awareness, and inadequate waste management infrastructure. The presence of waste degrades environmental, aesthetic, health, and socio-economic quality. Plastic waste, in particular, poses persistent threats due to its durability and chemical composition, contributing to marine pollution, microplastic proliferation, and reduced tourism appeal. Addressing coastal waste requires a comprehensive understanding of its types, sources, and contributing factors, alongside improved public awareness and sustainable waste management strategies.

Keyword: Coastal waste, Marine pollution, Plastic debris, Environmental impact, Waste management

Rubbish

Waste itself in the Republic of Indonesia Law No. 18 of 2008 concerning Waste Management, is the remains of human daily activities and/or natural processes in solid form. Waste can be defined as material or objects that are discarded and have reduced value, thus waste can have added value again if managed so that it can be reused and does not pollute the environment (Mahyudin, 2014). Meanwhile, in the scope of coastal areas there is a definition of marine waste which is interpreted as solid material originating from humans that is thrown into the sea or that reaches the sea through various sources such as waterways or household and industrial waste channels (Rees & Pond, 1995). Waste can be categorized into 3 types with different characteristics (Ratnasari et al., 2019), namely

- 1) Organic waste is waste that comes from living things, such as humans, animals, and plants. Organic waste itself is divided into wet organic waste, which has a high water content, such as vegetables and kitchen scraps. Then, small organic waste, which has a low water content, such as firewood and dry leaves.
- 2) Inorganic waste, waste produced from non-biological materials that cannot be broken down by nature, which can also be produced from synthetic products and mining technology processes, examples of inorganic waste are objects made from plastic and cans.

3) B3 waste or hazardous and toxic waste is waste that contains hazardous or toxic materials due to its nature, concentration and quantity that can damage the environment and endanger human health both directly and indirectly. According to Republic Law No. 18 of 2008 (2008) concerning Waste Management, B3 waste is specific waste that includes waste containing hazardous and toxic materials, waste containing B3 waste, waste arising from disasters, demolition of building debris, waste that cannot be technologically processed and waste that arises periodically.

According to Nurmaisyah & Susilawati, (2022) waste can be divided into several types based on its group, including:

- 1) Wet waste or waste whose main components consist of organic materials that rot easily, this type of waste mostly comes from food scraps, animal corpses, and so on.
- 2) Dry waste or waste whose main components consist of metal materials such as scrap metal, used cans, and there is also non-metal dry waste such as paper, glass, ceramics, stones and textiles.
- 3) Soft waste or waste with a soft texture such as dust that comes from the decay of houses or buildings and also from wood shavings.
- 4) Large waste or waste that comes from household equipment such as tables, chairs, refrigerators, washing machines and other household equipment.

According to (NOAA, 2021), waste is categorized into several types which can be seen in Table 1 following.

Table 1. Waste Category according to NOAA

Category	Type
Plastic	<i>Plastic fragments (film fragments, foam fragments, hard fragments), plastic bags and pouches, beverage bottles, bottle caps, plastic containers, food wrappers, glasses, pipettes, cutlery, plastic packaging rings, cigarettes, matches, fishing floats, fishing bait and lines, ropes and nets, balloons, beauty tools and products, and other plastics.</i>
Metal	Metal scrap, aerosol cans, canned or aluminum beverage containers, and other metals.
Glass	Glass pieces of glass beverage bottles, jars or jars, and other glass.
Rubber	Rubber chips, latex, sandals and shoe soles, tires, and other rubber.
Wood	Cardboard, wood building materials, paper and cardboard, paper bags, and other wood products.
Processing	
Fabric or textile	Fabric scraps, clothing and shoes, pillows, dolls, face masks, non-rubber gloves, rope and fiber netting, towels and rags, and other fabrics.

Waste management in every region has inhibiting factors that often occur as factors that are difficult to avoid, such as population density and distribution, the physical and socioeconomic characteristics of the environment, the surrounding culture, the attitudes, behaviors and habits of local residents and visitors (Sahil et al., 2016). The factors that can influence waste production according to (Indramawan, 2014), are:

- 1) Population, population is the main factor that influences waste production because of course the more the population, the more products or goods that can become waste after they are no longer used, so that waste management also has to keep pace with the rate of population growth.

- 2) Socio-economic conditions, socio-economic conditions can be a factor that can increase the amount of waste per capita that is thrown away. The amount of non-biodegradable waste will increase depending on the socio-economic conditions in an area according to the circumstances and needs of the community and the available materials, the higher the socio-economic conditions will increase construction activities and building renovations, the increase in transportation, agricultural products, industry and others will be a consequence of the increasing amount of waste that will be produced.
- 3) Technological advances, technological advances with increasingly diverse raw materials and manufactured products will increase the amount of waste produced, which will also increase and become more diverse.

Sources of Waste in Coastal Areas

Coastal areas are defined in Article 1 number 2 of Law Number 1 of 2002.(2014) Regarding the amendment to Law Number 27 of 2007 concerning Coastal Areas and Small Islands, coastal areas are transitional areas between terrestrial and marine ecosystems that are strongly influenced by climate change on land and at sea. It is generally believed that most plastic waste comes from land sources, especially areas that have a higher probability of being a source of waste in the ocean such as population centers, ports, tourist destinations, and landfills, in addition to river estuaries also contributing as the main route for waste to enter coastal areas to the sea (Cloux et al., 2024; González-Fernández et al., 2021). Beach use has been shown to be a major contributor to waste along the coast and river estuaries (Storrier et al., 2007). Ease of access to the beach is a major factor in the increasing number of beach visitors. Beaches that are closer to main roads are generally more accessible and have a larger number of visitors, thus potentially producing more waste (Willis et al., 2017). In addition to land, waste can also come from activities at sea such as shipping, fishing, aquaculture and also from oil and gas extraction (Thiel et al., 2013). According to Dainur (1995), (Patuwo et al., 2020)waste sources can be divided into several categories, namely:

- 1) Household waste.
- 2) Waste from markets and public places such as stalls, shops, recreation areas
- 3) Street trash
- 4) Industrial waste
- 5) Offices, schools and companies
- 6) Agriculture and plantations
- 7) Mining
- 8) Fisheries and livestock

Factors that Influence the Existence of Waste

The factors that influence the existence of waste can also be divided into categories that can influence each other between existing factors (Saptenno et al., 2022), namely:

- 1) Knowledge, the importance of knowledge as a basic foundation for all actions and character of a person, especially in this case related to waste management. Many areas have not participated or even not held counseling on waste management, which has an impact on the lack of public knowledge about waste. So that with a lack of knowledge, people consider throwing garbage on the beach or into the sea as a habit that is easy with minimal further effort in waste management without considering the future impact.

- 2) Attitude, related to feelings and actions based on experience, considerations, and understanding experienced in waste management whether throwing garbage on the beach or into the sea is a wrong attitude or not, so that with a society that has a positive attitude and is aware of sorting and managing garbage properly will be a good step because it will avoid the accumulation of garbage especially in areas with the attraction of natural beauty.
- 3) Human behavior, activities or activities that are assessed and observed by others directly or indirectly are the concept of behavior (Notoatmodjo, 2007). A person's behavior greatly influences waste management, selfish people who only prioritize personal satisfaction rather than public interest will be detrimental in waste management so that it can cause environmental damage. People's behavior towards waste is diverse, behavior that can be detrimental is when they know the negative impacts of waste but still let it be.
- 4) Public awareness, which occurs when the previous three points have been addressed, will lead to a public awareness of the importance of environmental cleanliness through proper waste management to create a clean, beautiful, and healthy environment. However, if public indifference to waste is allowed to persist, it will lead to environmental degradation, impacting the quality of life of residents in a region.

The Impact of Waste

Damage and aesthetic degradation of coastal areas are among the impacts of waste pollution that require attention. In addition to aesthetics, increased waste pollution can disrupt shipping and reduce seawater quality, which can impact the health of marine life and humans, even leading to death (Nurmawati et al., 2018). These impacts significantly impact many aspects, which can be described as follows.

- 1) Declining Environmental Quality
The presence of waste, especially plastic waste, in landfills, coastal areas, and oceans can pose an environmental threat due to the characteristics of this material which is very difficult to decompose. Plastic can cause environmental damage slowly but surely in various ways, starting from toxic chemicals from plastic that will contaminate the soil and water and even the air to directly harm animals that accidentally consume it. When plastic is in the ocean, especially in the form of smaller particulates, it not only affects the marine environment physically, but also pollutes seawater with toxic chemicals that impact marine organisms and ecosystems (Faure et al., 2015). With data from 2015 showing that the global level of plastic production reached 270 million tons, with approximately 100 million tons ending up as plastic waste on beaches. Of that amount, poorly managed coastal plastic results in the entry of 8 million tons per year ending up in the ocean. These plastics decompose slowly polluting water bodies and endangering marine life. Microplastics have also been detected globally in rivers, lakes, and oceans affecting ecosystems worldwide (Anwar Zainu & Rahman Songip, 2017).
- 2) Declining Quality of Public Health
During its manufacturing process, plastic is combined with various chemicals that can pose significant health risks (Sharmin et al., 2016). Beyond the production stage, plastic waste itself poses significant health hazards, contributing to air, soil, and water pollution, and exposing humans to toxic and carcinogenic substances. Ingesting microplastics can exacerbate these health risks, potentially causing inflammation and digestive problems. Furthermore, air pollution resulting from the

incineration of plastic waste can cause respiratory and cardiovascular problems. Waste workers are also at high risk because they can be exposed to hazardous chemicals during their work in handling and disposing of waste (Fayshal, 2024). These health risks underscore the importance of regulating plastic production and improving disposal practices to protect human health and the ecological balance.

3) Declining Aesthetic Quality of Beaches

Coastal areas, including their aesthetic appeal, are key tourism assets. However, beaches are also a major source of microplastics, and the accumulation of beached debris substantially impacts the future abundance of microplastics in the marine environment (Hinata et al., 2024). This exacerbates the detrimental impacts on scenic beauty, disrupting the beach's aesthetic quality and reducing the value of tourist destinations. Among the problems associated with the decline in beach aesthetics due to debris, coastal erosion remains the most significant (Defeo et al., 2009; Lukoseviciute & Panagopoulos, 2021). Coastal erosion and ecosystem degradation will be further exacerbated by climate change (Lukoseviciute & Panagopoulos, 2021), and flooding is likely to further damage the beach's aesthetic quality.

4) Declining Socio-Economic Quality of Coastal Areas

The problem of waste in the environment, especially in coastal areas, proves that the general public's view of waste on the beach is very important because it will affect the income of the surrounding community, starting from the reduction of tourists, damage to infrastructure and tourism, the decline in activities that depend on the fisheries sector, and the damage to the local, national, and international image of the coastal area (Philipp, 1993; Tudor & Williams, 2003). The loss of tourism and recreation potential is a very real impact of the influence of marine debris. Coastal communities that are highly dependent on the tourism sector for their livelihoods can experience a drastic decrease in income due to marine debris. Of course, people prefer to visit clean beaches, with land and waters free of trash, rather than beaches containing various types of marine debris, people can even avoid certain beaches if they feel the view or appearance of the beach is not worth visiting (Tudor & Williams, 2003).

Summary

This article discusses waste issues in coastal areas, covering definitions, classifications, sources, contributing factors, and impacts. Waste includes organic, inorganic, and hazardous materials, often originating from households, tourism, industry, and marine activities. Coastal areas are highly vulnerable due to land-sea interaction and human behavior such as littering and lack of awareness. The accumulation of waste—especially plastic—leads to environmental degradation, health risks, aesthetic decline, and socio-economic losses, particularly in tourism-dependent communities. The article emphasizes the need for public education, behavioral change, and improved coastal waste management to prevent further ecological and economic damage.

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